

DEEP LEARNING BASED AUTO ACCIDENT AND EMERGENCY ALERT SYSTEM

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INTRODUCTION

Road accidents are one of leading cause of deaths and injuries around the world; thus, making it very significant for road safety. Traditional systems for detecting accidents usually depend on the human element for their operations and this creates delays in emergency response due to human involvement.

Due to development of deep learning and computer vision automated detection of car accidents will not only be possible; but also practical. In order to qualify how an accident has occurred will be done by analyzing and processing real-time video and/or images to instantly establish that an accident has occurred and to contact the appropriate authorities.

The use of deep learning models (e.g. CNN) and object detection algorithms (e.g. YOLO) allows obtaining and using features that would not be obtained using basic computer vision methods to establish patterns of accidents that have occurred, such as vehicle collision or abnormal traffic flow, thereby increasing accuracy and reducing response times to accidents, ultimately saving lives.

LITERATURE SURVEY

1. Detection Based on YOLO:

Summary: Detection of accidents in real-time using object recognition and tracking in video streams.

Steps:

Extract video frames from live and/or recorded sources.

Recognition of vehicles using YOLO, along with moving track on vehicles.

Algorithm used: YOLOv3/v4/v5, IoU, Kalman filter.

Advantages:

Real-time interaction/processing speed.

Highly accurate recognition of objects.

Ideal for use with CCTV/live monitoring.

Disadvantages:

Requires GPU/computationally intensive.

Will have lower processing capabilities in high-density populated areas.

High sensitivity to light/weather conditions.

2. Classification Based on CNN:

Summary: Classifies images to detect accidents.

Steps:

Extract and pre-process video frame images.

Prepare a CNN model to be used for classification.

Algorithm used: CNN, VGG16, ResNet.

Advantages:

Simple to implement and train.

Less computational requirements.

Can be used effectively on labeled data sets.

Disadvantages:

No detection of motion/sequence.

Cannot be used in real-time applications.

Accuracy is dependent upon image quality.

3. CNN + LSTM Model:

Summary: Video based accident detection using both spatial features (CNN) and temporal features (LSTM).

Steps:

Extract the same sequential video frames.

Use CNN for spatial features and LSTM for temporal learning of sequence.

Algorithm used: CNN, LSTM, GRU.

Advantages:

Uses both motion and temporal patterns for analysis.

Higher accuracy than when using only single models.

Allows for effective use of data in video analysis.

Disadvantages:

More complex architecture.

Requires large database for training/cannot use reduced data sets.

Length of time to complete all training and computation.

4 Optical Flow Technique

Description: An accident detection mechanism based upon assessing differences between movement occurring between consecutive frames.

Procedure:

o Optical flow vectors are generated and computed for frames; the difference is utilized for determining sudden motions or movement abnormalities

o Algorithms: Lucas-Kanade, Farneback

Advantages:

- Less resource-intensive & quicker than deep learning
- Effective for detecting movement
- Does not require large quantities of training data

Disadvantages:

- Susceptible to noise and light variance
- Cannot classify types of objects
- Less accurate than deep learning algorithms

5 Machine Learning Algorithms

Description: Accident predictions which utilize previous historically structured data (i.e. speed, traffic, weather).

Procedure:

- o Historical, structured data is obtained and pre-processed
- o Machine learning model to be trained for prediction purposes
- o Algorithms: Decision Tree, Random Forest, Support Vector Machine

Advantages:

- Supportive in overall reduction of accidents
- Minimal computational costs
- Applicable with structured data

Disadvantages:

- Cannot be used for real-time accident detection
- Prediction accuracy is reliant upon quality of data used to train machine learning model
- Limited to use with vision-based application

6 IOT + Deep Learning System

Description: Objective is to provide reliable and accurate accident detection and alert mechanism by combining sensor measurements from multiple sources and using deep learning techniques to validate accident detection.

Procedure:

- o Impact from external force is detected via sensors (accelerometer, Global Positioning System [GPS])
- o Accident is validated through utilization of deep learning techniques
- o Algorithms: Convolutional Neural Network [CNN], You Only Look Once [YOLO], Sensor Thresholding

Advantages:

- Provides the most reliable and accurate solutions
- Will provide fast response to emergency services
- Data from multiple sources can be combined for improved reliability

Disadvantages:

- The cost associated with hardware configuration can be very high
- Requires ongoing maintenance and calibration
- Integration of all systems can become quite complex

PROPOSED SYSTEM

The suggested automated system of detecting accidents on the road automatically via an AI algorithm that utilizes machine learning to continuously monitor traffic conditions and detect accidents with no human involvement in the detection and classification of accidents. The system utilizes the video taken by a CCTV system, or the recorded video of a location, which can then be divided into frames and resized/normalized/enhanced to create accurate detection. The system uses the frames to detect vehicles on the roadway and locate the location of abnormal events, e.g., sudden vehicle to vehicle collisions; vehicle deformation; abnormal motion of vehicles (no longer travelling in a forward direction). By classifying based on the above criteria, the system will classify the condition of traffic, i.e., either "normal" or "accident". If there is an accident detected, the system will automatically send an alert to emergency services and provide them with:

- Location of accident
- Time of accident
- Evidence of the accident via a picture of the accident.

If an accident is not detected, the system will continue to monitor the roadway. Using this technique, accidents can be detected quickly, which reduces the amount of time required for emergency services to respond to an accident, as well as improves the safety of roadways.

METHODOLOGY

Figure(1) Flowchart of the automated road accident detection system using deep learning.

ALGORITHMS USED

This system will utilize both deep learning and computer vision techniques to conduct highly accurate accident analysis.

- The YOLO (You Only Look Once) algorithm will serve as a real-time object detection system for detecting vehicles in accidents as well as detecting vehicle-to-vehicle collisions using images from a video camera or CCTV (closed circuit television) camera.
- A convolutional neural network (CNN) will be used as feature extractor/classifier to extract features from the images that correlate to specific types of accidents (for example, identifying damaged vehicles) and to classify what occurred at the time the initial image/object was taken.
- Long short-term memory (LSTM), if needed, will increase the accuracy of detecting real-time video accidents by capturing temporal information (for example, from a video). Capturing the motion of objects and how they interact with each other can help improve the accuracy of video detection of accidents.
- By using optical flow (the detection of motion/or movement from frame to frame), movement will be detected between frames for video prior to and during an accident. Sudden changes in the speed of vehicles will indicate sudden motion changes during an accident.

INPUT

Figure(2):Sample traffic scene used as input for automated road accident detection

OUTPUT

Figure(3): Detected vehicle with number plate recognition during accident analysis.

Figure(4): Real-time accident detection system output showing alert, vehicle number, time, and location.

Figure(5):Emergency alert message sent with location link after accident detection.

MATHEMATICAL EQUATION

1. Convolution Operation (Convolutional Neural Network)

$$S(i,j) = (I*K)(i,j) = \sum_m \sum_n I(i - m, j - n) * K(m,n)$$

I = input image

K = kernel or filter

S = feature map

2. Activation Function (Rectified Linear Unit)

$$f(x) = \max(0,x)$$

- Introduces non-linearity
- Removes negative numbers from output

3. Loss Function (Binary Cross-Entropy)

$$L = -[y * \log(p) + (1 - y) * \log(1 - p)]$$

y = true label

p = predicted probability

4. Intersection over Union (IoU) – You Only Look Once (YOLO)

IoU = Area of Overlap / Area of Union

- Measures how accurate an object was detected
- Larger IoU = better accuracy

5. Example Equation for Long Short Term Memory (Simplified)

$$f_t = \sigma(W_f * [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_f)$$

- Decides what information to keep or forget
- Important for remembering past input sequences

WORKING ARCHITECTURE

Architecture:

- Video input → Frame extraction → Deep Learning model → Accident Detection → Alert system

Working:

- Input Module:
 - Takes video input from CCTV / Camera
- Preprocessing:
 - Converts video to frames
 - Resizes and normalizes images
- Detection Module:
 - Uses a CNN or YOLO model
 - Detects vehicles and collisions
 - Analyzes motion and sudden changes
- Decision Module:
 - Classifies:
 - Accident
 - No Accident
- Alert Module:
 - Sends an Alert with:
 - Location
 - Time
 - Captured image/video
- Key Features:
 - Real-time Detection

- High Accuracy
- Automatic Alert System
- Reduced Human Intervention

FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

Potential future improvements to the system:

Detection of accident severity (minor/major)
GPS - For precise location tracking
5G & IoT - For increased communication speed
Edge Computing via Raspberry Pi or Camera systems
Predictive Models to minimize accidents prior to occurring
Smart City interface with traffic control systems
Auto-Emergency Response Systems

Research for the future also indicates the potential to improve accuracy & compatibility of multimodal data and transformer based models.

CONCLUSION

Deep Learning based, Automated Detection of Road Accidents can greatly increase road safety and speed of response by detecting accidents using Machine Vision and AI technologies in real-time with high accuracy.

This advanced technology provides great benefit to smart cities as well as their traffic management systems by integrating AI based deep learning models, real-time video analysis, and Automatically alerting other drivers and authorities when an accident occurs.

There are some challenges with implementing this type of system due to the availability of data and variations in the environment, but advancements in AI are moving quickly and will eventually improve the robustness and deployability of these systems.

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